

Horses in ancient works: A symbol of power and identity in different cultures

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Abstract

The horse has always had a high status in ancient civilizations. This animal, beyond being a tool for transportation or war, has become a symbol of concepts such as power, courage, nobility and freedom. This symbolic role is clearly visible, especially in the literary, mythological and artistic works of various civilizations, especially in Iranian culture. The aim of this research is to examine and analyze the role and position of the horse in ancient literature, history and culture, art and illustration, myths and legends in order to explain its cultural and social effects on different societies. To find out the question of how the role and position of the horse in ancient literature, history and culture, art and illustration, myths and legends is explained and what effect does it have on the formation of cultural symbols and concepts in different societies? We used a library method based on note-taking and extracting materials from various sources. The results of this study indicate that the horse, a noble animal, has always played an important role in human civilization and this animal has been a symbol of power, nobility, freedom and connection with nature, not just a compound. The horse has inspired artists and writers, been a vital element in wars and conquests, part of customs and traditions and a sacred symbol in myths. Ultimately, the horse is an integral part of human identity and culture, and examining its role leads us to a deeper understanding of history and art and reminds us of the importance of preserving this heritage.

Keywords: Horse, Ancient Literature, History, Culture, Mythology, Legend

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